

Black Silicon Solar Cells

Grøn Dyst

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Concept: Nanostructured solar cell

- Increased surface area + structures on the order of light-wavelengths
- Improved absorption material for solar cells

Nanostructures

$\text{SF}_6 + \text{O}^-$ ions

Process Advantages

- Process:
 - Upscalable: RIE-chambers can potentially be HUGE!
 - Fast, simple and cheap method:
 - 4 minutes process time, maskless process.

Optimal Structure

Mag = 61.74 K X

EHT = 2.00 kV
WD = 8 mm

Signal A =
Photo No.

Structure Data:

Peak Height \approx 100 nm

Process: 4 min RIE

Improved Absorption

Reflectance

Quantum Efficiency

Quantum Efficiency

IV-characteristics

IV-characteristic for nanostructured and blank solar cell

Data for nanostructured cell:

$V_{OC} = 0,56 \text{ V}$

$I_{SC} = 6,5 \text{ mA}$

$J = 34,6 \text{ mA/cm}^2$

Efficiency = 11,8 %

Fill Factor = 61 %

Higher Photocurrent

Efficiency of the solar cells

Power conversion efficiency of **11,8 %** for nanostructured solar cell compared to

7,9 % for blank reference!

State-of-the-art

- VLS-growth

- Kayes, Lewis et al., California Institute of Technology, CA

$$\eta = 0,46 \%$$

- Chemical Etching

- Peng et al., Tsinghua University, Beijing

$$\eta = 9,31 \%$$

- This Project:

$$\eta = 11,8 \%$$

Conclusion

- A new kind of solar cell – based on nanotechnology – introduced
- Promising results: Nanostructures improve efficiency of solar cells (with $\approx 4\%$)
- Further optimization and improvements
- Potentially improving existing solar cells' efficiency + creating new kinds of solar cells for the future

Thank you!

